

“MANAGEMENT EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES A STUDY OF INDIAN SCENARIO”

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Abstract

Management education in India has come a long way from the 1960s when there were limited number and types of business schools in the country. With the increase in the number and types of business schools there are growing concerns about maintaining the quality of management education in the country. In the process of globalization, management education in India is playing key role in coping up with the rapid changes taking place in all types of business activities. The focus is on maintaining good quality of education in thousand plus management institutions in India. These institutes are operating in almost all corners of the country. They are diverse in nature, size and structure. The disparity is because of several socio-economic and regional factors influencing working of these institutions. There is no doubt that Indian educated managers are in good demand in both developed and developing countries. But something is missing within this, so this fact should be identified to eradicate a gap of management education in developed and developing countries.

*Received 01 August 2021, Accepted 17 August 2021, Published 31 August 2021
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I-INTRODUCTION:

Management education in India is fast undergoing a radical change. The two current developments sweeping India, namely liberalization and globalization, have had a considerable impact on management education. Today there are a large number of management institutions in the country. This vast number of Business Schools needs to satisfy a series of questions. This being so, the other side of the story shows the concern for the Business School professors is how to produce good managers with the attributes of increased efficiency and effectiveness, ethics, knowledge, fluency to apply management concepts, theories and tools.

Management Institutes in India from 1950 to 2010

Period	No. of Institute Increased	Avg. Increase
1950 to 1980	118	4.00
1980 to 1995	304	20.00
1995 to 2000	322	64.00
2000 to 2010	1073	107.30

Source: Dayal.I. “Developing Management Education in India”

II-OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The main objectives of this study are as follows

1. To study about the relevance of Management education in India
2. To study about the various situations under which management education is imparted in India
3. To study about the quality concerns of management education in Indian scenario.
4. To study the situation of Indian management education with developed countries management education

III-METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

Secondary data is widely used from all the available sources i.e. published and unpublished literature related to the present study.

IV-MANAGEMENT EDUCATION IN INDIAN SCENARIO:

- ❖ Non-availability of qualitative teachers in most of the parts of India due to various reasons
- ❖ Lack of proper motivation/ reorganisation to efficient/qualitative teachers if available
- ❖ Lack of case study pattern of study as compared to developed countries education
- ❖ Inadequate Library and Lab facilities in most of the parts of India
- ❖ Poor placement record in many management institutions due to non- employability of students and no proper initiation from management of institutions
- ❖ Lack of awareness to students about the future and prospects of management education because they only seek degree/diploma
- ❖ Excessive burden on management teachers which leads to non-creativity in them in day to day activities
- ❖ Competition to increase management education institutions and students intake no interest in improving infrastructure by most of the management institutions
- ❖ No industrial exposure to students which does not create entrepreneurs ability or interest among them
- ❖ No linkage between industry and institution which leads to interest towards academic sectors only they do not go for industrial side
- ❖ No proper motivation to management teachers for their academic achievements and research orientation among management teachers
- ❖ Lack of professionalism in management institutions from top to bottom due to unawareness of quality/standards of management education

V-SUGGESTIONS TO IMPROVE THE PRESENT SCENARIO IN INDIA:

Following are the important suggestions to strengthen management education in India which is a fast developing country in the world

- Recruitment of efficient/qualitative management teacher to get good output from institution for matching the industrial requirements
- Creation of professionalism in management institutions for better results
- Restriction of number of institutions and students intake by AICTE/UGC for better service and quality of management education
- Conducting more number of placements so as to employ students in right time
- Improvement of infrastructure in the institute for teachers and students to enhance knowledge of both to compete the world
- Motivating management teachers for research and industry interactions for good output from their end to students
- Organizing more number of industrial tours within and outside the country to make aware students about practical management skills and their practices in different situation
- Establishment of entrepreneur development cell in management education institutions
- One semester should be designed for practical exposure by making practical training compulsory before the award of management degree.
- Encouragement for MOU between institute and industry/universities/foreign universities or institutions
- Providing digital library and latest journals/books/case studies to students and teacher to update their knowledge and improve standards of teaching and learning
- Provision of relevant specializations as per employment demand at institute level to make students available for right requirement in industries

- Creation of Alumni association of management students and frequent interaction with them and updating them about the present and future prospects available to them

VI-CONCLUSIONS:

Management education imparted by IIMs is on one hand and management education imparted by other institutions in on other hand. There is a big gap between these two. So this gap must be filled first to come on par with developed countries. Following are the major conclusions.

- ✓ The existing system of Management Education is alienated from real life. There is a gap between the subjects and the objectives and this cannot achieve such goals as national development, building an ethical, religious and spiritual values in business etc.,
- ✓ Professionalism in MBA Education –by creating an individual body by an Act of Parliament like for ICAI/ICWAI/ICSI.- this will assure balance of management education with developed countries.
- ✓ The infrastructure and facilities must include classrooms with multimedia and projection facilities, latest computers and peripherals and a good library with collection of books on all management subjects of world class, this will lead to standards on par with developed countries

In short every management institution in India must feel it is their responsibility to impart quality education, this will lead their students to compete other management students in the world especially developed countries. This will bring the greatest satisfaction among all

REFERENCE S:

- Adam, D, (1998), “Defining education quality: educational planning”
- AICTE, (2010), “List of approved institution for the management institution, 2000-2010”
- Bhasker Rao, Accord consultants (P) Ltd, Bangalore, “Presentation at the one day Seminar on Industry-Institution Interaction”
- Chaudhary, H.C., (1993), “Management education in India: past, present and future” Deep Publications, New Delhi
- David L Deberitin and Stephan J.Goetz, (1994), “Differences in Rural and Urban Schools: Issues for Policymakers”
- Reported opinions expressed by academicians at the Roundtable discussion that appeared on BUSINESS WEEK Online,
- Shadaksharappa K.B., Manager- Training, Trident Software Ltd, Bangalore: Presentation at the one day Seminar on Industry-Institution Interaction
- Singh S.B., (2007), “Globalization and Management Education in India”
- Varun Arya, - "Sustaining Quality in Management Education" article appeared Indian MBA.com